

PSYCHOLOGICAL DIFFERENCES BETWEEN CHILDREN WITH MANY CHILDREN IN A FAMILY AND ONLY CHILDREN

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Adolescents from families with different children are all considered leaders in solving problems, but their methods are different. While adolescents from large families are based on cooperation and mutual understanding, adolescents with only one child require support from those around them.

Considering the environment in large families, most researchers conclude that the personality traits of a child depend on the size of the family. The size of the family, the order of birth of the child determine the important characteristics of the child's personality[1].

Children growing up in large families are inflexible, have difficulty finding their bearings in uncertain conditions, and develop conformity rather than independent thinking. They are more anxious, sensitive, and need constant encouragement. They have a lower level of self-awareness, higher levels of self-control, higher levels of organization, and leadership qualities, as well as high rates of hostility and suspicion of others.

Children with siblings are more resilient, less selfish, tend to cooperate with other children, and respect their parents. Children from middle-sized families are distinguished by their emotionality and extroversion.

Children from large and small families develop various personality changes and deviations. They are prone to suicide and a high level of delinquency. As they grow up, they commit serious crimes, drink and smoke. Girls from families with four or more children begin to have early sexual life and have problems with pregnancy. Children from single-child families have a high level of anxiety, which can develop into high neuroses.

Kindergarten children from large families are often frustrated in emotional and stressful situations. School children (younger schoolchildren) are characterized by such characteristics as thoughtfulness, calmness, caution, and seriousness. Only children are

more playful, active, cheerful, prone to risk-taking, and they overestimate their own capabilities.

Second-grade children from large families are characterized by emotional stability, sociability, and composure. By the sixth grade, the characteristics of the children change. They become reactive, excitable, impulsive, irritable, emotionally unstable, and have low self-confidence[2]. Only children, on the contrary, are very excitable and impulsive in their younger school years, but become emotionally stable and composure in adolescence.

Senior students from large families are submissive, obedient, benevolent, polite, intrapunitive, impulsive, but at the same time proactive, realistic, and insightful. Only children are diligent, self-confident, stubborn, extrapunitive, prone to conflicts, as well as sentimental, emotional, and intuitive.

Senior students from large families have higher levels of responsibility and tolerance, they feel full responsibility for their actions and deeds, and are able to provide impartial, disinterested assistance to those around them[3]. Senior only children have higher levels of independence, need for dominance, suspicion, and distrust.

Adolescents from large families demonstrate higher levels of self-confidence on the scales of character and dexterity.

Children from large families are exposed to cooperation, mutual assistance, and compromise with many family members from childhood, which is why they develop socially adaptive personality traits, which can lead to a positive assessment of their own character[2]. It is common for children from large families to be involved in household problems and tasks in life. This is the basis for the development of their work skills and qualifications and a high assessment of their own skills.

Emotional reactions in frustrating situations differ between children from large families and single children. Students from large families are characterized by an intrapunitive ego-protective reaction[3].

Extrapunitive and intropunitive orientations depend on the age of the students and the type of family. Second-graders from large families react to frustrating situations in an extrapunitive manner, while their teenagers often react in an impulsive manner[1].

Thus, in emotionally stressful situations, children from large families try to protect their "I" through self-blame, remorse, and guilt. At a younger school age, they begin to make high demands on those around them. In adolescence, they try to resolve the situation in a compromise way, solving the problem through mutual understanding and concessions. Younger school-age single children are characterized by an approach of cooperation and compromise, and in their opinion, any dispute will eventually lead to

a solution. Older schoolchildren are characterized by external accusations and high demands on the people around them.

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